

Low cost marine robotics and their usage in the real world

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The rapid pace of commercial hobbyist grade electronics for aerial drones has ushered in a new generation of low-cost marine robotic systems. Using components from Torrance based Blue Robotics, aquaculture and many other fields are undergoing a revolution in capability and affordability.

2. Aim

To document the real-world utility and robustness of cheap underwater robotics hardware.

3. Material and methods

The BlueROV2 and other enclosures and electronics from Blue Robotics have been utilized by Catalina Sea Ranch, along with technology from PME and others to accomplish monitoring of their offshore aquaculture sites.

4. Results

Numerous inspection surveys and recovery methods have been enabled by the utility of the low cost capable BlueROV2.

5. Conclusions

Low cost motor and enclosure technology is developing new applications for underwater robotics systems at a breakneck pace.

6. Keywords

ROV, Marine Robotics, Depth, Aquaculture, Scientific Monitoring

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Author biography

Tony White Tony has a Mechanical Engineering degree from Georgia Institute of Technology and has been a consulting engineer for the Company since 2016. Tony designed the electrical and mechanical systems for the NOMAD buoy that transmits real-time data for monitoring environmental conditions and providing security at the Catalina Sea Ranch's aquaculture facility. For the past four years, he was a mechanical design & development engineer with Ocean Lab/Apium that pioneered swarm robotics vehicles in marine environments. Previous to that, Tony was a mechanical engineer with C&C Technologies/ASV Global, a hydrographic survey company that designs and constructs autonomous boats, semi-submersibles and AUVs.

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